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STUDY OF THE FACTORS INFLUENCING POLITICAL SOCIALISATION OF STUDENT COMMUNITY IN MUMBAI

Political Science

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Mumbai is one of the most important metropolitan cities in India which is known for its dynamic politics. In both popular and academic literature Mumbai has always been a centre of attraction for numerous academicians and scholars. It provides a replica of regional politics since political underpinnings in Mumbai has indirect influence on politics of Maharashtra. The most dynamic and active force engaged in political activity is the young college going students. It is because of their resourcefulness and vigorous political activity almost all political parties are in competition to induct them within their fold.

Such situation provides a space to research and study how the process of political orientation of the college students takes place in a metropolitan city like Mumbai. It is for this reason the author has attempted a small research to enquire how political socialization of student community in Mumbai takes place. The writer actually surveyed around fifty students in different colleges in Mumbai and endeavored to inquire the process of Political Socialisation.

Political socialization is the process by which people come to acquire political attitudes and values. Political socialization is a process that takes place in every society. This process begins very early in life and is a continuous process. Generally, the main aim of political socialization is to create good citizens. The current research was undertaken to study the process

of political socialization and the factors influencing such socialization in Mumbai. It is important to discuss meaning of political socialization before exploring the topic further.

Political socialization is a process by which individuals learn about politics and the factors which shapes political culture. It is claimed that political socialization as a concept is somewhat new. Almond and Verba who studied the problems and effects of political socialization on political activities gave serious thinking to this concept. Followings are three main stages of political socialization.

The first stage is when a child begins to realize that there is a world around him. Then, he realizes that outside the family there are more powers. He/she starts living and learning outside family. They put certain demands on the society and recognize authorities, which operate in the society. Second stage is when one reaches adolescence stage and becomes mature enough to participate in political activities.

Third stage is when either he/she begins to love or hate surrounding political institutions and systems. At this stage, values and attitudes become clear. It should be noted that sociologists have been more interested in how people related to groups and society, social psychologists have been interested in how individuals learn about and adjust to the demands of groups and society, and anthropologists have been interested in how people learn about their culture.

Political socialization is an attempt to train people to do what the system requires in values, norms, information and skills that are considered desirable and useful in the society. Almond and Verba defined political socialization as a process by which political cultures are maintained and change. Followings are some of the important type of political socialization.

1) Manifest socialization: Certain values and feelings towards a political system are directly expressed. There is an explicit communication of information to other partis e.g. formal education given in educational institutions, talk on electronic and mass media about political problems, and use of platform for audience. Such a manifestation can be both voluntary and involuntary. It includes all types of propaganda. It is not necessary that such a manifestation will

be for the maintenance or stability of political system, rather it can be for instability, change and even revolution.

2) Latent manifestation: There is no direct approach to the problems, and that ideas are transmitted indirectly. It is a method of transmission of non-political attitudes, which effect analogous roles and objects in the political system.

3) Particularistic socialization socialization: Political ideas of individuals are directed towards a Particular socialization value, which they are required to adhere and appreciate. Thus, all political energies are directed in that direction alone.

4) Universalistic socialization: Here, political energies are not directed in one direction, but a cosmopolitan outlook is developed. One then can learn and perform several roles. Such roles can be in any walk of life.

5) Affective socialization: Stress in only on emotional values. There is a very little role of rationality. The values get changed with the changes of emotions and as such there is no much of stability.

6) Pragmatic socialization: In this type of socialization, stress is not on emotions, but on reasoning. The whole approach is pragmatic and all strategies are quite well planned and calculated and their good or bad effects are well understood.

Well, the process of political socialization is to create a nominal interest among the people, to inculcate value, discipline, and teaches people to become obedient, and to inculcate some lofty values. Political socialization acquired at three levels --- cognitive, emotive, and evaluative.

Importance of political socialization for the political system

David Easton says that political socialization creates a reservoir of support for political system. He further adds that political system is a set of human interactions in which authoritative allocation of values take place. In political system we have input, output, adaptation, and

maintenance. Political socialization is the adaptation and maintenance function of political system. Political socialization is interested in maintaining the status quo. The whole exercise of political socialization is to exercise order and stability, and normally political socialization is a pro-stable process.

In the present study the researcher interviewed fifty young individuals who were college going students. These Participating individuals were from the age group of 20-24 years. The interviews were conducted in a mutually decided, un-interrupted and calm location with the aim of getting the best responses. The interviews were conducted individually and were given a look of a normal discussion. The interview questions were designed so as to study political Socialization. These are the following questions which were asked to the students from colleges.

1. Questions relating to Political awareness

In order to better understand political socialization it is essential to gauge the extent to which the participating individual is politically aware. Questions were designed to know how many steps the individual takes to gather political information from various sources.

2. Questions relating to Political reality

What is the knowledge and approach (emotional and intellectual) of the individuals regarding the political reality existent in India.

3. Questions relating to Political expectations

These questions were designed so as to understand the participating individuals' expectations from the political bodies. Current events were discussed so as to make the interview interesting.

Analyzing Interviews

The researcher met the interviewees individually at their own house or in college campuses for discussions. They knew that there was going to be an educational interview and therefore seemed to have come prepared with some current information regarding politics. It is

essential to note here that the students were from different educational background and from different streams.

For the purpose of hiding the exact identity of the participant, respondent numbers were given to them. During the interview, the researcher learnt that many students were not regular reader of newspaper and they rarely took interest in political news. Though their political awareness was not really good, they presented fair in the overall interview because they had come prepared for it. They somewhat knew the facts about political reality in India like caste and politics or communalization of politics. However, their expectations from politics were unrealistic. This can be mainly because they did not know the facts and figures. They were more into a dream world concerning the political abilities. These were the students who were not member of any of student organization in Mumbai; they also never got a membership of any reputed social organisation. The members of student organisation performed very well, the probable reason being that they both were students who were active in political actions.

Discussion

The students who were not active in campus politics were hesitant and this was mainly because of their feeling of not being knowledgeable enough in this field of talk and discussion. These assumptions about the feeling of not being knowledgeable enough in political subjects were also reflected in their nervousness. The sources of media and Internet were used by the interviewees as a mode of entertainment or education in the subject of their study and specialization. They as students were more concerned about their career and though had great expectations from the government were not inclined to participate in any of the political activities.

The role of school and education on political socialization has been studied and identified by several researchers the education related to politics helps grow the positive seed of political socialization in the life of students. Thus, education is an essential part of growth relating political socialization.

Considering the larger activities and mission as stated by the student organisations and its adherence with the values of justice, reciprocity, community building, and participatory

democracy the researcher examined the connection between the campus's actual relationships with its surrounding community.

It is concluded that the theoretic relationship with the community often differs from the real. A number of student organisations appear to promote service and community outreach as ways to make themselves appear relevant but actually do not seem interested in any real commitment to the outlying community i.e. the students. These student organisations view the students as potential supporter of their parent political organisation and therefore get engaged in solving their personal and academic problems.

Many campuses do not attempt to orient students to the neighbourhood outside the campus, leaving it to individual students to become self-educated about the community. Oftentimes there are physical barriers between the university and the community that augment the disconnection between them. Community service centres on campuses (if they exist at all) often lack adequate resources, staffing, and funds. Overall, it has been found through this research that colleges and universities do not teach the community building/organizing skills that they need. They rarely provide models for healthy communities, either on the campus itself (where the hierarchical nature of the institution often overlooks student needs/input when making decisions), or through relationships with Universities often see service and civic engagement through a philanthropic lens, resulting in token gestures (i.e., their "excess" time, talent, and resources) to the community.

They seem to view service more as a public relations strategy, while in reality, they keep the community at arm's length the surrounding community. Many campuses view engagement in communities in terms of what the institution can do for the community, instead of how they can work together for the benefit of both. This leads to the exclusion of community members in university plans that affect the community.

Analysis

When provided opportunities through education, students understand and act upon the distinction between service—which encourages us to think that individual actions are a substitute for focusing on larger structural issues—and political activity—which involves working with

others to influence (or alter) societal institutions. They recognize and appreciate the value of service-learning in connecting their personal actions to larger social action.

They see service-learning as a primary vehicle for connecting service with broader social and political dimensions. Students are also closely attuned to the processes and institutional context for service learning. Through community-based experiences, they increasingly appreciate the ability of educators on campus to help make the connections between their work in the community and the knowledge and skill base that deepens their community work. Students often find that traditional faculty is unable to make the deeper connections because they live too exclusively within the disengaged and isolated culture of academia.

Democracy and Education

Students often find that traditional faculty is unable to make the deeper connections because they live too exclusively within the disengaged and isolated culture of academia. Additionally, students find that the most effective teachers and mentors for their community work and those who help the most in making connections to larger social issues—and offer the most in terms of shaping their career goals—are likely to be the staff members who administer the campus community service centre. These people embody more closely the students' ideal of being situated both on campus and in the community.

At the same time, students experience a curricular deficit: some of the most important knowledge and skills we need for community-based work—around advocacy, organizing, conflict resolution, community economic development, etc.—are not taught in any courses or through any programs on campus. As students look elsewhere to acquire these community competencies, their campus life becomes less relevant to their civic aspirations. Student participation in larger social issues is also directly impacted by the institutional environment, which may only be tangentially related to service-learning. Students are subtly conscious of and respond to the campus climate as it relates to political activity. This can be experienced in ways related to the kinds of opportunities that are made available. This consciousness was studied and analysed by asking them following questions:-

Is there a community service center on campus?

Are there opportunities to enrol in service-learning courses?

Are there forums on campus for dialogue about larger social issues?

If so, who is allowed to take part?

Does the rhetoric of public service and being a good neighbour belie the realities that the students experience in the local community?

Are students encouraged to challenge the administration about campus policies?

Is adversity of political voices brought to campus? Are students reprimanded or punished for political activity that associates them—directly or indirectly—with the institution?

To what degree is democracy practiced on campus?

The New Student Politics

The students' community was confounded to realize that higher education does not concentrate its full potential upon alleviating social ills. It is worth noting that students do not express anger at this revelation; they express disappointment. This reaction may be self-serving: Students, like many others, are unwilling to indict systems that they need. Moreover, to indict higher education may have larger, personal implications for students. Students often reside in college communities that allow them the freedom to assume multiple identities, to negotiate power and privilege, and to examine the complexity of democratic tenets like inclusion and access. In such a community, students are attuned to how agents of the institution model these tenets. Students pay close attention to where these individuals and their beliefs stand in the priorities of the institution.

The younger students described faculty who risk their careers—tenure and promotion—to pursue a pedagogy of responsible civic engagement; marginalized service centres crowded into basements and crumbling houses that are engaged in transformative community work; poorly paid community service directors with little access to power; community partners who are denied access to institutional resources and career centres and external affairs offices that promote limited markers of success. Institutions send these powerful signals to students and community

members about where their civic priorities lie. Higher education should take note: The students from Mumbai region were remarkably attuned to the ways in which community service centres that are not integral to the pedagogical mission “let the institution off the hook.” As the institution points with pride to its community service centre, and presidents preach about empowering students, these marginalized centres become an excuse for institutional disengagement from the community.

It is argued that the leaders of colleges and universities often consider the voices of trustees and donors to be more important than that of their students, creating an academic atmosphere that is not necessarily conducive to civic engagement. Presidents should instead “practice what they preach” to their students, by facilitating quality service-learning opportunities. In addition, students are generally unaware of how to participate in the college community.

They know little about the administrative functions of higher education and are organizationally illiterate about the particular universities they attend. Many of us who do try to navigate the bureaucracy often lack access to the institutional system and find progress to be painstakingly slow and difficult. We often don’t understand the inner workings of our institutions until we are well into our college careers; by then it is often

Democracy and Education

It is conceivable that colleges and universities do not educate students about their bureaucratic pathways just so that students will not try to “reform” the system. The energy required to navigate and translate the bureaucracies is often too great a hindrance to overcome, which further contributes to the perception that college students are apathetic, even on their own campuses.

A perception many people have about college students is that our movements lack focus. The writer here argues that although many student movements have multiple goals, they are, in fact, highly organized. As one student noted, “we confront power and the lack of democracy [on many levels], but that does not mean that we lack focus.” Students are also uneasy with the fact that their generation is being held accountable to a different generation’s standards of political

involvement, such as those of the Civil Rights Movement in the 1960s. We believe that through our work in community service we effectively confront some of the same “-isms” and institutional inequalities that the Civil Rights Movement challenged.

This Declaration makes many observations about students that may be well-intentioned, but are not well-founded. One concern we had with the Presidents’ Declaration is that it implies that college students are in dire need of assistance. As one student commented, it seems like the signers of the Declaration are saying “Okay, kids are falling apart, we’ve got to help fix them and save them.” While we as students want to work with college faculty and administrators, these are not attempts at self-preservation. We would like to be in respectful conversation with faculty and others at our schools, and to work with them on community building and civic engagement.

Analysis

One major theme that came out of the current research is the importance of student voice. In Mumbai it was clear that students are not provided sufficient opportunities on campus to voice their social and political concerns in constructive and effective ways. Students want to be consulted about their thoughts, opinions, and feelings on important public decisions and issues, especially those that affect them directly as members of a campus community or as community builder’s off-campus. Institutions must investigate ways to engage in conversation with students from many different areas of the college in order to make a greater commitment to incorporating student voice into discussions and decision-making. Student representation in administrative areas should not be limited to one token student sitting on a number of committees. In addition, it is not merely enough to talk with students; their input should have equal weight when compared to the input of other stakeholders in the decision making process. One important point students made is that they are often organizationally illiterate about the colleges and universities that they attend.

In order to facilitate student participation and student voice on campus, students must be educated about the inner-workings of campus bureaucracy. Colleges and universities should not fear students who attempt to navigate administration in hopes of making changes on campus.

Students should also be viewed as producers of knowledge, not consumers. For example, they should be encouraged to work with other students and professors on research projects that focus on community problems and social issues. In addition, community service should be given legitimacy and value as an important part of a student's educational experience. Colleges and universities across the nation should make a commitment to finding new ways to foster student voice and incorporate student concerns into discussions and decision-making. If students, faculty, administration, and community partners are able to work together, they will have the potential to successfully address important campus and community issues.

Political Engagement

At the outset students expressed frustration about the derogatory ways in which they are often characterized by college and university presidents, faculty, and the public regarding their levels of political and civic engagement. The writer of this chapter argues that, we are politically engaged, although we may participate in politics in unconventional ways. This study described three distinct forms of political engagement: conventional politics, community service, and "service politics." Conventional politics focuses on the role of government to protect individual rights; promote interests; and provide needed policies, laws, and services.

Inferences from the Statistical Analysis

The study relies more on primary data the statistical analysis and the inferences drawn from that need to be looked in a great detail. This chapter initially deals with the variables that were used to understand the awareness of the students towards the Social Economic and Political Inequalities and Privileging Dissent, Privileging Rights and Decentralisation. And then tries to examine their relations to understand their impact on political socialization and the role played by the student organizations

To understand any political process political culture becomes one of the indicators. These indicators when work with above variables gives us a clear picture of the underlying social and political processes. Based on the above literature, above variables were identified and then studied to build relationships to reach to assess the outcomes.

The above two variables and one indicator has attempted to study the following three hypothesis.

- Q.1 Does political socialization have an impact on ensuring the public outcome of cognitive orientation of the students in Mumbai and what are the socio political paths through which such an impact is achieved?
- Q.2 Does political socialization have an impact on ensuring the public outcome of affective orientation, and what are the socio political paths through which such an impact is achieved?
- Q.3 Does Political socialization have an impact on ensuring the public outcome of evaluative orientation, and what are the socio political paths through which such an impact is achieved?

Variables

(i) **Impact of political socialization (PS) on cognitive orientation**

The very purpose of **PS** has been oriented towards making the people more cognitive towards political objects like the political parties, pressure groups. Political science literature has often been oriented toward studying how bureaucracies can be engaged with to ensure accountable organizational performance (Meier, Polinard and Wrinkle, 2000). Accountability is a measure of the sensitivity of governance to the people whom it must serve. Political Socialisation enforces accountability by ensuring that administrations have to respond in a time bound manner to citizens.

(ii) **Impact of Political on Affective orientation of the Students**

Affective orientation is an important aspect of welfare state governance and through which one looks as whether the policies and programmes affect the lives of individuals and impact on the larger public life and citizenry. Affective orientation is sought by knowing how the students are policised.

Theory shows that failure in public organizations emerges in the form of chronic underperformance over a period of time unlike sudden collapses of organizations seen in

the private sector (Meier and Bohte, 2000). These failures are often the result of organizations being burdened with multiple, contradictory and diverse goals beyond their existing capacities. Affective orientation through PS can help citizens to monitor public organizations better and help them deliver effective governance.

(iii) Impact of Political Socialisation on evaluative

Evaluation of governance and party politics has been an important element of political science which advocates methods such as collaborative planning and deliberative democracy, advocacy and protest. (Innes and Booher, 2000). Activists in India have argued that students have a more constructive role to play in this regard. In terms of evaluative orientation it can become a political project which seeks to re-envision governance by enabling a dialectic of knowledge, that between governmental and subaltern ones.

(iv) Impact of Political Socialisation on Decentralisation

Canaleta, Arzoz and Garate suggest that political decentralisation leads to the amelioration of regional inequalities. In territorially large societies, decentralisation of power and authority is necessary for effective development. Decentralisation refers to the process of sustaining grass root collectives which hold governance at various levels accountable to them. It is hoped that due to manifest political socialization, grass roots processes will ensure that vibrant discussions take place and the implications of different views are taken into account.

(v) Impact of PS on Privileging Dissent

The prohibition of dissent is a part of the colonial legacy which holds that the only natural position for citizens to hold is that of affection for the state. Dissent which is an important political challenge to totalitarianism can be enabled by both manifest and latent PS as citizens become empowered to question the basis of administrative decisions. It is hoped that due to PS, the ideals of dissent will keep public spaces of deliberation and dialogue alive and prevent a vibrant polity from becoming dormant.

(vi) Impact of PS on Privileging Rights

PS can ensure that administrative officials including ministries are indeed

answerable to citizens and institutions such as the Central Information Commission (CIC) follow up with the concerned ministries and direct them to release information on receiving complaints from citizens. PS can induce potential to become important privileging rights as other public spaces such as the media are characterized as being not only stenographers to power but participants in the abuse of power . Ps provides an opportunity for safeguarding a multiplicity of rights as aberrations can be pointed out and violations can be interrogated in serious ways. PS indicates that rather than rights being composite of an inherent contract, they are part of a continuous struggle to achieve justice.

(vii) Impact of PS on Social Inequality

Even in unitary structures of governance, education and health are usually decentralised subjects to ensure that they can be transparently governed and monitored by local stakeholders. This is particularly necessary as those who have suffered historically from discrimination on the basis of caste or religion, can be empowered to access important aspects of life such as education and health. AmartyaSen (1999) has argued that in societies where information is freely available, developmental freedoms can be accessed by those who live on the social margins. PS can play an important role in addressing social inequalities as it can become a political instrument that questions discrimination on a parochial basis. Enclosures which discipline and demobilise people are opened up for empirical scrutiny through cognitive, affective and evaluative orientations.

(viii) Students Attitude towards Economic Inequality

Economic concentration can also be understood in terms of employment being available only in centralised locations (Garcia-Lopez and Muniz, 2010). With respect to the changes taking place in the capitalist organisation of production, workers' organisations need to reflect the decentralised realities that have emerged from capitalist re-organisation. PS can help developing a consensus in questioning economic inequality as it seeks to bring out wrongdoing which oppresses people. When people are not allowed to collectivise to fight for their rights, PS which may turn into defiance, demonstrations opens up spaces for collective deliberation and formation.

(ix) Impact of PS on Political Inequality

In the face of political inequality, the oppressed often discover ways of subterranean resistance which subverts the control of the dominant. In this context, PS can be seen as another weapon of the weak, which facilitates the enactment of everyday resistance. Activism provides an opportunity in subverting hierarchies in the interest of democratic justice as the state is made accountable to citizens, and administrators can no longer pursue feudal fiefdoms. If it is felt that privatisation and managerialism are causing damage to the socialist fabric of society, then the use of PS enrooted through student organization opens up the possibility of empirically enquiring this damage. Political inequality can be addressed when different views of what the political collective must look like are discussed in the light of prevalent marginalisation's and injustices.

Scale Development

In order to understand the impact of Political Socialisation on variables like social inequality, Political inequality and economic inequality, scales were developed. These scales give us a brief idea of the types of inequalities prevailing in the society and the impact of the same on the implementation of Right to Information.

Similarly, the scales were developed for the mediating variables like privileging dissent, privileging rights and decentralization. Dependent variables like the cognitive orientation, Affective orientation and evaluative orientation were also developed. Following are scales that were developed and for the purpose. Further EFA and Kaiser Meyer Olkin (KMO) test was conducted on the scales to understand the reliability of the scales developed. Whichever scale loaded two components in the scale reliability test and EFA, those inputs were withdrawn before conducting the regression analysis.

Scale Development for Impact of political socialization on students' attitude with reference to Social Inequality:

To develop a scale for measuring the impact of students attitude on social inequality, eight items were generated from literature review and conversations with PS activists, and they are listed below:

Label	Item
si1	PS ensures that the urban homeless can access governance
si2	PS ensures that those suffering human rights abuses can access governance
si3	PS ensures that women who have faced gender discrimination can access governance
si4	PS ensures that Dalits who have faced caste discrimination can access governance
si5	PS ensures that religious minorities who have faced discrimination can access governance
si6	PS ensures that the physically disabled who have faced discrimination can access governance
si7	PS ensures that those who have faced marginalization due to living in backward areas can access governance
si8	PS ensures that vulnerable people like fishing and forest communities can access governance

An Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was conducted using Varimax Rotation.

The Kaiser Meyer Olkin (KMO) index was 0.881, which was above 0.5 and the Bartlett's test of sphericity had a p value of 0.000 which is less than p value of 0.05 and thus significant.

The items loaded on factors and the rotated component matrix is shown below:

Component Matrix^a

	Component
	1
si1	.729
si2	.813
si3	.842
si4	.854
si5	.812
si6	.812
si7	.789
si8	.373

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

a. One Component Extracted

The items load only on one factor and the variance explained is 58.885% which is above the required level of 50%, indicating good validity for the scale.

	Component
	1
si1	.751
si2	.821
si3	.850
si4	.864

si5	.817
si6	.821
si7	.798

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

a. One Component Extracted

Each of the factor loadings is above 0.5, reinforcing that the items validly measure the variable social inequality (si).

The cronbach's alpha for the scale of social in social inequality (si) is 0.668, which is above 0.6, indicating good reliability.

Scale development for impact of political socialization on students attitude towards economic inequality

To develop a scale for measuring the impact of students attitude on economic inequality, eight items were generated from literature review and conversations with PS activists, and they are listed below:

Label	Item
ei1	PS ensures that farmers facing agrarian distress can access governance
ei2	PS ensures that unemployed youth can access governance
ei3	PS ensures that informal workers can access governance
ei4	PS ensures that contract workers can access governance
ei5	PS ensures that the poor can access governance
ei6	PS ensures that daily wage labourers can access governance
ei7	Ps ensures that migrant workers can access governance

ei8	PS ensures that those with insecure livelihoods can access governance
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An Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was conducted using Varimax Rotation. The Kaiser Meyer Olkin (KMO) index was 0.879, which was above 0.5 and the Bartlett’s test of sphericity had a p value of 0.000 which is less than p value of 0.05 and thus significant.

The items loaded on two factors and the rotated component matrix is shown below:

	Component	
	1	2
ei1	.697	.071
ei2	.215	.958
ei3	.815	-.010
ei4	.863	.154
ei5	.891	-.157
ei6	.883	-.162
ei7	.889	.087
ei8	.856	-.205

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

a. Two Components Extracted

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.

As ei2 loads on another factor, it is dropped and the EFA was conducted again. Now the items load only on one factor and the variance explained is 71.434% which is above the required level of 50%, indicating good validity for the scale.

	Component
	1
ei1	.695
ei3	.816
ei4	.858
ei5	.896
ei6	.887
ei7	.884
ei8	.862

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

a. One Component Extracted

Each of the factor loadings is above 0.5, reinforcing that the items validly measure the variable economic inequality (ei).

The cronbach's alpha for the scale of social in economic inequality (ei) is 0.932, which is above 0.9, indicating good reliability.

Scale development for impact political socialisation on political inequality

To develop a scale for measuring the impact of PS on political inequality, eight items were generated from literature review and conversations with PS activists, and they are listed below:

Label	Item
pi1	PS ensures that those who have little voice in legislative processes, have access to governance

Label	Item
pi3	PS ensures that those who have little voice in judicial processes, have access to governance
pi4	PS ensures that those who represent marginalised political positions, have access to governance
pi5	PS ensures that those who are viewed as dissenters by dominant political positions, have access to governance
pi6	PS ensures that those who are resisting the injustices of the state, have access to governance
pi7	PS ensures that those who have little voice in electoral politics, have access to governance
pi8	Ps ensures that those who are suffering from political victimisation, have access to governance

An Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was conducted using Varimax Rotation. The Kaiser Meyer Olkin (KMO) index was 0.865, which was above 0.5 and the Bartlett’s test of sphericity had a p value of 0.000 which is less than p value of 0.05 and thus significant.

The items load only on one factor and the variance explained is 56.294% which is above the required level of 50%, indicating good validity for the scale.

The items loaded on factors are shown below:

	Component
	1

pi1	.824
pi2	.879
pi3	.733
pi4	.815
pi5	.292
pi6	.764
pi7	.785
pi8	.751

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

a. One Component Extracted

Each of the factor loadings is above 0.5, reinforcing that the items validly measure the variable political inequality (pi).

The cronbach's alpha for the scale of political inequality (pi) is 0.718, which is above 0.7, indicating good reliability.

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